

Shedding Light on Pseudoreplication in Statistics for Life Science Students

Bethany J. G. White¹, Yipeng Rao², Jinqiu Liang³
^{1,2,3} University of Toronto, 27 King's College Circle, Toronto, Ontario M5S 1A1

Abstract

Statistical errors in life sciences research may lead to inaccurate and misleading findings and therefore contribute to reproducibility concerns in science. One common error is pseudoreplication. This is a form of model misspecification where models assuming independent observations are fit to dependent data. In this paper, the impact of pseudoreplication is explored through results of recent simulation studies that were motivated by published life sciences studies. Implications for teaching and learning statistics in life sciences and future research are then discussed.

Key Words: pseudoreplication, data literacy, teaching with authentic data, statistical reasoning

1. Introduction

Statistical errors are prevalent in life sciences research and are contributing to reproducibility concerns in science (Weissgerber et al., 2016). There have been many calls for improvements to training (Gardenier & Resnik 2002, Weissgerber et al. 2016, Baker 2016). Yet, undergraduate life science students may only need to complete one statistics course toward their programs, if that (Tong et al., 2022).

A 2019 study conducted in an introductory quantitative research methods course for life sciences showed an improvement in student self-efficacy to select appropriate statistical procedures and to interpret statistical results by the end of the course, but there were still gaps in students' abilities to do both (White & Singh, 2021). In particular, two of the questions that were included on this survey are shown in Figures 1 and 2. Toward the end of the introductory statistics course for life sciences described in Tong et al. (2022), White & Singh (2021) found that fewer than 5% of the n=126 student respondents selected the most appropriate answer to the question in Figure 1 (i.e. we cannot conclude anything from the Chi-squared test because the measurements are not independent). Since the most popular answer (over 40% of respondents selected this option) was the third option shown in Figure 1, students appeared to be inappropriately using the reported Chi-squared p-value to draw a conclusion (White & Singh, 2021). The question in Figure 2 was included on the survey as well to see if students were able to select a statistical procedure appropriate for dependent samples. The most popular answers to this question were "a paired t-test" and "one-way ANOVA", with approximately 30% selecting each option. Fewer than half of the students chose a method that would be appropriate for dependent samples. These results suggest that students did not seem to recognize dependency in data, nor the inappropriateness of standard statistical methods which assume independent observations for the dependent measurements in these research scenarios toward the end of the course (White & Singh, 2021).

In a paper published in *Nature Neuroscience* (Fig. 1a), researchers classified rod terminals in the retina as either bipolar (+) or not bipolar (-). Using a total of six mice (three for each genotype, either “wild-type (+/+)” or “Pikachurin knock-out (-/-)”), they examined whether the proportions of the two rod terminals differ between wild-type (+/+) and Pikachurin (i.e., a protein involved in photoreceptor formation) knock-out (-/-) mice.

What can we conclude from their Chi-Square (χ^2) test (Fig. 1b)?

Fig 1. b: Quantatative analysis of bipolar dendrites in the wild-type(+/+) and *Pikachurin*(-/-) mouse retina. 260 and 391 measurements were taken from the 3 mice in the wild-type and knock-out groups, respectively. χ^2 Test; P-value<0.001

- Mice with the Pikachurin knock-out (-/-) tend to have a smaller proportion of bipolar terminus (+) than wild-type mice, so this proportion seems to depend on genotype.
- There is not a statistically significant difference in the proportions of bipolar terminus (+) for wild-type (+/+) and Pikachurin knock-out (-/-) mice, so the proportion does not seem to vary based on genotype.
- There is evidence against equality of the proportions of bipolar terminus (+) in wild-type (+/+) and Pikachurin knock-out (-/-) mice, suggesting this proportion differs based on genotype.
- We cannot conclude anything from this statistical test because the measurements are not independent.
- I do not know

Figure 1: Question included on White & Singh (2021) survey to gauge students’ ability to recognize pseudoreplication given a research question and data

You are in a laboratory course where you are working with a group of students to collect data on the effects of different drugs on blood vessel constriction. The experimental apparatus is set up so that an artery is mounted on a contraction measuring device in a bath. Different drug solutions can be added to the bath. The baseline contraction is measured, then the contraction is measured after adding Drug A, and again after B. After administering Drug A, the bath is emptied and washed out before Drug B is added. Each group of students uses one artery sample. The class results are summarized in the following table:

Group #	Contraction force (g) at baseline - No drug	Contraction force (g) after Drug A	Contraction force (g) after Drug B
1	2.9	2.3	4.1
2	2.8	3.1	3.8
3	3.2	3.5	4.7
4	3.0	2.6	4.2
5	2.9	2.9	3.9
6	2.6	3.8	5.2
7	2.6	3.2	4.3
8	2.9	2.5	4.0
9	2.8	3.1	4.6
10	2.7	3.0	4.7

If you are trying to compare the efficacy (i.e. contraction-inducing capability) of these treatments, what statistical technique would be most appropriate?

- a) chi-squared (χ^2) test
- b) independent samples t-test
- c) one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA)
- d) a paired t-test
- e) random effects model
- f) repeated measures ANOVA
- g) simple linear regression
- h) Kruskal–Wallis test
- i) I do not know

Figure 2: Question included on White & Singh (2021) survey to gauge students' ability to select a statistical procedure for dependent samples given a research question and data

It is not only novice researchers like the students who participated in the White & Singh (2021) survey study who make such errors. The use of statistical procedures which assume independence on dependent observations is called *pseudoreplication* and it is a far too common error in life science research that can lead to inaccurate and misleading results (Lazic et al., 2018). In a review of the 19 research studies published in a single issue of Nature Neuroscience in 2008, Lazic (2010) discovered pseudoreplication in 12% of the papers and another 36% were suspected of having pseudoreplication but lacked sufficient detail to confirm. In a more extensive PubMed search, Lazic et al. (2018) reviewed papers published on studies where experimental treatments were applied on at one level (e.g., parents) but effects were explored at another level (e.g., offspring) between 2011 and 2016, and they detected pseudoreplication in close to half (i.e., 46%) of the 200 papers reviewed.

In this paper, we will explore the impact of pseudoreplication by highlighting the results of two simulation studies that were motivated by published life sciences studies. We then discuss the implications for teaching and learning of statistics in life sciences and suggest instructional

strategies that may help prepare our students recognize and avoid pseudoreplication in their future research endeavors.

2. Exploring the Impact of Pseudoreplication through Simulation Studies

2.1 Quantitative Response with Matched Pairs

Student's t-tests are commonly taught in introductory statistics and used in research. An error that may occur while performing t-tests is to ignore matching between two samples, leading to the inappropriate use of a two-sample t-test when paired t-tests, or equivalently, one-sample t-tests on differences between measurements, would be more appropriate. Distinguishing between these t-tests and being able to decide when each is appropriate for a given research question and data is crucial as the misuse of either test can give misleading results.

Both tests assume that the data arise from simple random sample(s) from the population(s) of interest. The paired t-test requires the differences between each pair of measurements to be normally distributed, while the two-sample t-test requires the measurements within each sample to be normally distributed. There are potentially substantial differences in the degrees of freedom; the degrees of freedom for a paired t-test is $N - 1$, where N is the number of pairs of measurements; whereas the degrees of freedom for a two-sample t-test will be somewhere between $\min(N_1, N_2) - 1$ and $N_1 + N_2 - 2$, where N_i is the number of measurements for the i^{th} sample, depending on whether the standard deviations of the response can be considered equal for the two groups (i.e., pooled or unpooled two-sample t-tests). The purpose of the simulation study described in this section is to explore the impact of conducting unpooled two-sample t-tests on paired samples.

2.1.1 Simulation Motivation

Schömig et al. (2021) describe their study on spine surgery investigating the effect of perioperative anaemia on postoperative spinal implant infection (PSII). They used Haemoglobin (Hb) and haematocrit (Hct) levels as indicators of anaemia and compared pre- and post-operative Hb and Hct levels (and the changes from pre- to post-) between 50 septic and 50 aseptic patients. Septic and aseptic patients were matched based on multiple variables including age, body mass index (BMI), diabetes status, American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) scores, and smoking habits. The authors reported means, standard deviations, and p-values for "Student's t tests" to compare Hb and Hct levels for the matched aseptic and septic patients. However, there did not seem to be sufficient information reported to determine whether a two-sample t-test (pooled or unpooled), or the more appropriate procedure in this situation, a paired t-test, was used. Having said this, they also used chi-squared tests to compare categorical variables for the matched septic and aseptic groups, so there was pseudoreplication in that situation. P-values of less than 0.05 were considered significant.

The mean difference between the pre-operative and post-operative Hb levels was found to be 3.45 ± 1.25 g/dL in the septic group, and 2.82 ± 1.48 g/dL in the aseptic group, resulting in a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.034$). The mean difference in pre-operative and post-operative Hct levels was 0.10 ± 0.04 g/dL in the septic group, and 0.08 ± 0.04 g/dL in the aseptic group, although this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.055$). Based on the t-test they conducted, they concluded an association between negative peri-operative Hb-trend and PSII. Although the authors determined the change in Hb and Hct levels as a difference between pre- and post-operative levels, it is not clear they conducted paired t-tests to compare these differences between the aseptic and septic patients. There may be pseudoreplication in this situation, and if so, the statistical results may be misleading.

With the study described above serving as the motivation, this simulation study aims to investigate the impact of the misuse of two-sample t-tests (unpooled) for paired samples and how this impact changes with sample size and effect size.

2.1.2 Methodology

This simulation study consists of two experiments; each involving different parameter values to assess the impact of the type of t-test employed on statistical results. Both experiments involve performing hypothesis testing on the same null and alternative hypotheses. The null hypothesis (H_0) assumes that the mean increase in Haemoglobin levels is the same in septic and aseptic patients ($H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$), while the alternative hypothesis (H_a) assumes that the mean increase in Haemoglobin levels differs between septic and aseptic patients ($H_a: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$). Each of the two experiments will be conducted in two parts. In the first part of each experiment, data will be simulated under the alternative hypothesis to examine the effect of the type of t-test (i.e., an unpaired two-sample t-test and a paired t-test) on statistical power. In the second part, data will then be simulated under the null hypothesis to observe the effect of the type of t-test on the type 1 error rate. Effect sizes will be varied in the first experiment and variance will be varied in the second experiment.

The original study appears to treat the two groups as independent and employs two-sample t-tests even though the aseptic and septic patients were matched based on multiple variables. The paired measurements were simulated as observations from the bivariate normal distribution with mean μ values informed by the statistics reported in the paper and ρ taking on 6 possible values (i.e., 0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 0.9) to vary the strength of correlation between measurements. N , the number of matched individuals in the study, takes on 6 different values: 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, and 100 to cover a wide range of sample sizes. α also takes on 4 different values: 0.01, 0.025, 0.05, and 0.1 to study how the results differ at different significance levels.

Throughout both parts of the first experiment that compares unpaired t-test and paired t-test performance at different effect sizes, three parameters will remain constant: $\mu_1 = 3.45$, $\sigma_1 = 1.25$, and $\sigma_2 = 1.48$. These were the statistics reported by Schömig et al. (2021) for difference in pre- and post-operative Hb levels for aseptic (1) and septic (2) groups, respectively.

First, data sets were generated under H_a at different effect size to compare power of the unpaired two-sample and paired t-tests. μ_2 was determined using the Cohen's d effect size formula (i.e., $\frac{\text{mean}_1 - \text{mean}_2}{\text{pooled standard deviation}}$) but using the other parameter settings rather than observed statistics.

To vary μ_2 five effect sizes using Cohen's d formula were used (i.e., 0.2, 0.35, 0.5, 0.65, and 0.8). These values cover a wide range of effect sizes and are used to obtain five different values of μ_2 : 3.18, 2.97, 2.77, 2.56, and 2.35 (rounding to 2 decimal places). By varying N , ρ , α , and μ_2 , 720 distinct sets of parameter configurations were generated. For each one, 4000 data sets were generated and analyzed. Then, to simulate data under the null hypothesis, μ_1 and μ_2 were both set to 3.45. Again, $\sigma_1 = 1.25$, and $\sigma_2 = 1.48$ were informed by the statistics reported in Schömig et al. (2021). By varying N , ρ , and α , 144 different parameter configurations were generated. For each one, 4000 data sets were generated and analyzed.

To explore whether varying the ratio of the population standard deviations would impact results, we conducted a second simulation experiment. For this experiment, two parameters were held constant: $\mu_1 = 3.45$ and $\sigma_1 = 1.25$. Again, these values were informed from the statistics reported in the Schömig et al. (2021) study. For both parts of the experiment, σ_2 was varied to take 5 possible values using a standard deviation (SD) ratio σ_2/σ_1 to explore different relative values of σ_1 and σ_2 . The five SD ratios investigated were 0.2, 0.5, 0.8, 1.2, and 1.5 so the five values of σ_2 were 0.25, 0.625, 1, 1.5, and 1.875. As in the previous experiment, the value of μ_2 will be different in each part of this experiment depending on whether H_0 or H_a is true.

To compare statistical power for the two t-tests, μ_2 was set to 2.82, which is the mean change in Haemoglobin level for the septic group in Schömig et al. (2021) and to examine type I error rates, the means were both set to $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = 3.45$. By varying N , ρ , α , and σ_2 , 720 different parameter configurations were generated. For each parameter configuration, 4000 data sets were generated and analyzed.

2.1.3 Results

Figures 3 and 4 compare the power for the two-sample (unpooled) and paired t-tests for different effect sizes and correlations. The paired t-tests appear to be consistently more powerful than the two-sample t-tests for $\rho > 0$ when we hold effect size and N constant. For both t-tests, power increases as effect size increases and as N increases.

In addition, when all parameters are kept constant, the paired t-test results in higher statistical power than the two-sample t-test, and the difference in power is the smallest at $\rho = 0.2$. When both N and effect size are small, conducting a paired t-test only results in slightly higher statistical power than a two-sample t-test. It is not surprising that power is low for small N and small effect size as it is difficult to detect a true difference in this context. However, when N is small and the effect size is large, the gain in power by conducting a paired t-test over a two-sample t-test is more evident and increases with ρ . The same happens when the N is large, and the effect size is small, performing paired t-tests results in much higher statistical power than performing two-sample t-tests. In contrast, when both N and effect size are large, power is close to 1 regardless of ρ and the type of t-test conducted; in other words, when N is large, both tests are able to detect true differences when the effect sizes are also large. As both N and effect size increase, they seem to impact power more than the type of t-test.

Figure 3: Empirical power plots for different effect sizes and select values of ρ , grouped by N ($\mu_1 = 3.45$, $\sigma_1 = 1.25$, and $\sigma_2 = 1.48$)

Both N and effect size affect the statistical power regardless of the type of t-test conducted. Overall, regardless of ρ , effect size, and N , the paired t-test results in higher statistical power for all parameter configurations, although the difference is more pronounced for smaller ρ , N and/or effect sizes.

Figure 4: Empirical power plots for each ρ at all effect sizes, grouped by N ($\mu_1 = 3.45$, $\sigma_1 = 1.25$, and $\sigma_2 = 1.48$)

In Figure 5, for all sample sizes and the 0.05 significance level (represented by the dashed lines in the plots), when conducting a paired t-test, the estimated type 1 error rate falls closely to the pre-determined significance level (α) of 0.05 for all levels of ρ . In contrast, when conducting the two-sample t-test, the estimated type 1 error rate is only close to the pre-determined α of 0.05 when there is no correlation between the two groups. The difference between 0.05 and the estimated type 1 error rate becomes wider as ρ increases. In fact, when ρ is high, the estimated type 1 error rate for the two-sample t-test at 5% significance level is close to 0 (i.e., H_0 would rarely be rejected).

Figure 5: Empirical type 1 error rate by ρ and N ($\mu_1 = \mu_2 = 3.45$, $\sigma_1 = 1.25$, and $\sigma_2 = 1.48$)

Figures 6-8 show results of the simulation study exploring the impact of the relative magnitude of variances on the performance of the two-sample and paired t-tests. At all values of N and standard deviation ratios, paired t-tests result in higher estimated power than two-sample t-tests. In addition, at each N , power is higher at larger values of ρ for both tests. Furthermore, when conducting paired t-tests, the power plots appear to display a parabolic pattern with SD ratio, especially for higher correlations, but this pattern appears to flatten as N increases. At $N < 30$, the estimated power of a paired t-test reaches its peak at an SD ratio of 0.8. However, as N increases and approaches 100, the

power at all SD ratios becomes close to 1. In contrast, when conducting two-sample t-tests, power decreases as σ_2 increases. Thus, at large values of N , the impact of N on power appears to be more prominent than the other parameters and the type of t-test. Moreover, as N increases, the SD ratio at which the difference in power is the greatest seems to increase (for all values of ρ).

Figure 6: Empirical power plots at all SD ratios and 3 selected values of ρ , grouped by N ($\mu_1 = 3.45$, $\mu_2 = 2.82$, $\sigma_1 = 1.25$, and $\sigma_2 = (\text{SD Ratio}) * \sigma_1$)

As is clear from Figure 7, the estimated power of the paired t-test for each SD ratio increases as ρ increases. In contrast, the estimated power of the two-sample t-test seems to decrease as ρ increases for smaller N . N seems to have a more evident impact on power than the other variables and the type of t-test performed because power seems high, regardless of test type and SD ratio for large N (e.g., see $N = 100$ in Figure 7).

Figure 7: Empirical power plots for each ρ at all SD ratios, grouped by N ($\mu_1 = 3.45$, $\mu_2 = 2.82$, $\sigma_1 = 1.25$, and $\sigma_2 = (\text{SD Ratio}) * \sigma_1$)

In Figure 8, the dashed line represents the pre-determined 5% significance level in each plot (i.e., $\alpha = 0.05$). At all SD ratios, by performing the paired t-test, the type 1 error always falls closely to

the pre-determined significance level of 0.05. In contrast, when performing the two-sample t-test, the type 1 error rate is only close to the pre-determined rate of 0.05 at $\rho = 0$. In addition, as ρ increases, the type 1 error rate of performing a two-sample t-test decreases, which means that as ρ increases, the null hypothesis becomes less and less likely to be rejected (i.e., the two-sample t-test is less likely to detect a difference).

Figure 8: Empirical type 1 error rate plots at each ρ , grouped by SD ratio ($\mu_1 = 3.45$, $\mu_2 = 2.82$, $\sigma_1 = 1.25$, and $\sigma_2 = (\text{SD Ratio}) * \sigma_1$)

2.2 Binary response with clustering

The previous simulation study explored the impact of using two-sample t-tests assuming independent samples on paired samples for a quantitative response. The second simulation study investigates the impact of a different type of pseudoreplication; one that arises when multiple binary measurements are taken on each experimental unit (i.e., there is clustering or multi-level data), but the resulting measurements are treated as independent in the analysis.

2.2.1 Simulation Motivation

Sato et al. (2008) present a study where they classified rod terminals in the retina as either bipolar (+) or not bipolar (-) for two genotypes of mice (i.e., Wild-type mice and Pikachurin mice). As described in the supplementary information published with Sato et al. (2008) “Eyes were enucleated from anesthetized mice (wild-type, pikachurin+/-, pikachurin-/- ; n = 3 each).”. Ultrathin slices of retinæ were then prepared and photographed, and the rod terminal were classified as either bipolar (+) or not bipolar (-). In their Figure 4e, Sato et al. (2008) display a bar chart comparing the proportion of bipolar (+) rod terminals for wild-type and pikachurin mice and report a chi-squared test p-value < 0.001 based on samples of sizes 260 and 361. However, there were only 3 mice of each genotype. There was pseudoreplication since they were treating the 260 and 361 measurements as independent for the purposes of the chi-squared test. Presumably, retinal measurements from the same animal would be correlated and there may be mouse effects. These features would both violate the independence assumption. Note that this study was the inspiration for the survey question shown in Figure 1. The simulation study described in this section aims to explore the effect of pseudoreplication in this situation. For the purposes of this simulation, datasets were generated assuming a mouse effect and correlated measurements within mice. Datasets were generated under four distinct scenarios, each designed to explore various effect sizes and correlation levels.

2.2.2 Methodology

Four effect sizes were explored, ranging from none (i.e., $p_1 - p_2 = 0$) to a large difference in the proportions of bipolar terminals (+) between the wild-type and pikachurin genotypes at a population level. Sample sizes similar to those in the paper were used (i.e., $n_1 = 260$, and $n_2 = 391$), but an assumption was made that the same number of measurements were obtained from each mouse of a certain genotype (i.e., 86 measurements for each wild-type mouse, and 128 measurements for each pikachurin mouse). This likely did not match the study exactly, but the individual mouse measurement counts were not reported and perhaps they were not even tracked.

Data were generated to build in a mouse effect and correlated measurements within mice. To achieve mouse effects, the proportion of bipolar terminals (+) was allowed to vary from mouse to mouse. Then, to simulate within-mouse measurements, values were generated with different levels of correlation ($\rho = 0, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5$). These correlation levels represent the degree of dependence among measurements, ranging from independent ($\rho = 0$) to moderately correlated ($\rho = 0.5$).

Beta distributions were used to simulate mouse-specific proportions of bipolar rod terminals in the retina. The beta distributions were parameterized by α and β values, which control the shape of the distribution and different values will be used to simulate the proportions for the wild-type and the pikachurin genotype mice. The three simulated probabilities for the mice in each genotype were then used to simulate bipolar (+) and non-bipolar (-) rod terminals as pairwise correlated Bernoulli observations with R function `rmvbin` in the `bindata` package (Leisch et al., 2021).

A chi-square test was then conducted to compare the bipolar (+) proportions in the wild-type and pikachurin genotype groups to mimic what Sato et al. (2008) did in their paper. Since we have knowledge of the parameter settings in the simulated datasets, we will be able to explore the impact of pseudoreplication and correlation in this situation. The null hypothesis is that rod classification (i.e., bipolar, or nonbipolar) and genotype (i.e., wild-type and pikachurin) are independent, while the alternative hypothesis is that the rod classification and genotype are dependent. Another interpretation of the hypotheses is $H_0: p_{Wild} = p_{Pikachurin}$ and $H_a: p_{Wild} \neq p_{Pikachurin}$.

Four different scenarios were simulated to represent varying levels of effect sizes:

- Scenario One (no effect): The null hypothesis (H_0) is true so the bipolar (+) proportion in wild-type and pikachurin groups is the same. Both mouse groups' beta distribution parameters were set to $\alpha = 100$ and $\beta = 100$, resulting in a mean of 0.5 for both genotypes.
- Scenario Two (large effect): The alternative hypothesis (H_a) is true so the bipolar (+) proportion in wild-type and pikachurin groups differs. The beta distribution parameters for the wild-type group will be $\alpha = 70$ and $\beta = 70$, and for the pikachurin group, $\alpha = 5$ and $\beta = 45$, resulting in a mean of 0.5 for the wild-type group and a mean of 0.1 for the pikachurin genotype.
- Scenario Three (moderate effect): The alternative hypothesis (H_a) is true so the bipolar (+) proportion in wild-type and pikachurin groups differs. The beta distribution parameters for the wild-type genotype were set to $\alpha = 70$ and $\beta = 70$, and for the pikachurin genotype, $\alpha = 35$ and $\beta = 82$, resulting in a means of 0.5 and approximately 0.3, respectively.
- Scenario Four (small effect): The alternative hypothesis (H_a) is true so the bipolar (+) proportion in wild-type and pikachurin groups differs. The beta distribution parameters for the wild-type genotype were set to $\alpha = 70$ and $\beta = 70$, and for the pikachurin genotype, $\alpha = 54$ and $\beta = 80$, resulting in a means of 0.5 and approximately 0.4, respectively.

The sample size and number of measurements per mouse were not varied in this simulation study. 1000 datasets were simulated under each scenario and for each of the four different correlation values ($\rho = 0, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5$). Empirical type I error rates and powers for the chi-squared test in these different scenarios were obtained and are presented in the next section.

2.2.3 Results

Figure 11 shows the estimated type I error rates when chi-squared tests were conducted on data that were simulated under the null hypothesis. When $\rho = 0$ (i.e., there was no within-mouse correlation between measurements), the empirical type I error rate was 0.102, considerably higher than the nominal significance level of 0.05. As the within-mouse correlation increases, the type I error rate increases dramatically so that it is just under 0.8 when $\rho = 0.5$. For all levels of correlation, use of the chi-squared test is inappropriate due to the mouse effect which is not reflected in the model. Therefore, it is not surprising that even when ρ is small, the chances of rejecting H_0 when it is true is much higher than the significance level of 0.05.

Figure 11: Empirical type I error rate by correlation under the null hypothesis

Figure 12 presents estimated power rates for the various effect sizes and correlations. When the difference in proportions is 0.1, the estimated power rate increases as correlation within each mouse type increased. The estimated power for this effect size is lower than that for larger differences in proportions (i.e., larger effect sizes). It is not surprising that a smaller effect size is more challenging to detect. As the correlation increases, however, the measurements become more similar, leading to an improvement in statistical power and an increased likelihood of detecting the effect.

Figure 12: Empirical power rates by correlation for different effect sizes under the alternative hypothesis

In contrast, for the larger effect sizes of 0.2 and 0.4, Figure 12 shows a different pattern. The estimated power rates decrease when the correlation is increased from 0 to 0.5. However, the higher the effect size explored, the higher the estimated power. For instance, when the difference in proportions is 0.1, estimated power ranges from about 0.65 to just under 0.8; whereas when the difference in proportions is 0.4, the estimated power ranged from about 1 to 0.95. This behavior suggests that a true difference can be detected even with at low correlations when the effect size is larger.

Based on Figures 11 and 12, the inappropriateness of the Chi-squared test in this situation is clear. This form of model misspecification will lead to questionable findings since there may be a very high chance of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is in fact true (Figure 11) or failing to reject the null hypothesis when it is false (Figure 12). Sato et al. (2008) reported a significant difference in bipolar terminals in retina of wild-type and pikachurin mice based on the Chi-squared test. However, this may have been a type I error.

3. Discussion

Using published research studies as motivation, we explored the performance of t-tests and chi-squared tests on dependent observations. Two different situations were explored: paired quantitative measurements, and a binary outcome with clustering and within-cluster correlation. In both contexts, we observed shortcomings with respect to the tests' abilities to detect real effects (power), and to not detect absent effects (i.e., type I error). In some of the situations, these shortcomings were quite dramatic. For instance, as shown in Figure 3, for smaller sample sizes and effect sizes, the empirical power is relatively low for all correlations, and considerable gains can be achieved by using the more appropriate paired t-test instead of a two-sample t-test for paired quantitative measurements. Based on Figures 11 and 12, it would be difficult to make any meaningful conclusion based on the chi-squared test conducted on these clustered binary data (with within-cluster correlation). For example, with a correlation of 0.5, the power when the difference in proportions is 0.1 is around 0.8 (Figure 12). However, if this very similar to the type I error rate when the correlation is 0.5 (Figure 11). Therefore, when correlation of 0.5 the chances

of rejecting the null hypothesis are just under 80% when there is no difference in proportions or there is a 0.1 difference in proportions.

These simulation results underscore the importance of recognizing and avoiding pseudoreplication in scientific research. It is critical that researchers be able to recognize situations where pseudoreplication may arise and take steps to avoid it. As discussed in the introduction, however, quite a few students and researchers appear to miss pseudoreplication in research. In the course described in Tong et al. (2022), students worked with real data, checked assumptions, and had plenty of experience distinguishing between paired and independent samples when deciding which t-test to use. Yet, when these students were surveyed toward the end of their introductory statistics course, many proceeded with methods such as chi-squared tests and ANOVA which were inappropriate for the dependent measurements in Figures 1 and 2 (White & Singh, 2021). Why is this? It may be that they are not recognizing dependency in the data, or perhaps they do not understand that it matters, and therefore opt to use statistical procedures typically used in their fields such as t-tests and chi-squared tests. Perhaps it is a combination of both reasons. Regardless, steps should be taken to help our students recognize pseudoreplication and the potential consequences of such errors. Given a research study, students will need to be able to recognize whether pseudoreplication may be an issue and be able to explain why it matters, as this will inevitably come up in their future research and/or when they are reviewing others' work.

More explicitly building dependent data structures and pseudoreplication into learning outcomes, class activities and assessments may help students recognize pseudoreplication and understand its risks. As per the GAISE (2016) recommendations, students should gain experience working with authentic data with multiple variables. Giving them hands-on experience thinking with messy data and even including data that is beyond the scope of the statistical methods they have learned to date would be helpful. Learning activities on independent and dependent data structures using a tool such as Common Online Data Analysis Platform (CODAP) would give students an opportunity to think critically about data structures and data origins (e.g., Halder et al., 2018). Also, exploring the impact of pseudoreplication with students through simulation studies such as the ones presented in this paper, and perhaps even setting similar simulation results up in Shiny apps (e.g., Wickham, 2021) for students to explore may help convince them of the potential consequences of the error. A couple of other activities we learned about at the 2023 Joint Statistical Meetings in Toronto that may help support our students learning about pseudoreplication include a "What Would Fisher Do" statistical modeling activity (Marina Ptukhina, "Understanding Model Construction Process in an Intermediate Statistics Course" presenter) and a "stakeholder analyses" (Rochelle Tractenberg, panelist in invited session "Incorporating social justice and ethics into the undergraduate curriculum"). The "What would Fisher Do?" activity (Bello et al., 2016) may help avoid misalignment between the data and the analysis such as pseudoreplication. If students worked through such an exercise for the data arising from Figure 1 and 2, it would be easier to recognize there are variables that should be included in the model which are not reflected in the chi-squared test or ANOVA (i.e., the mouse in Figure 1, and specific artery samples in Figure 2). A "stakeholder analysis" activity (Tractenberg, 2022) where thought is given to the various stakeholders of the research and the consequences of pseudoreplication from different stakeholders' perspectives would presumably help convince students of the potential seriousness of such an error and hopefully help them avoid it themselves and recognize it in others' research.

Pseudoreplication is an error that results in misleading findings. Using suitable statistical models will help ensure the rigor and credibility of findings, and ultimately, improve reproducibility in science. Therefore, we plan to integrate targeted class activities and assessments into our teaching practice going forward to help prepare students (i.e., tomorrow's researchers) to recognize and avoid pseudoreplication in research.

References

- Baker, M (2016) “1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility”, *Nature*. 533, 452-454.
- Bello, NM, Kramer, M, Tempelman, RJ, Stroup, WW, St-Pierre, NR, Craig, BA, Young, LJ and Gbur, EE (2016) "On recognizing the proper experimental unit in animal studies in the dairy sciences." *Journal of Dairy Science*. 99(11) 8871-8879.
- Gardenier, J and Resnik, D (2002) “The Misuse of Statistics: Concepts, Tools, and a Research Agenda”, *Accountability in Research: Policies and Quality Assurance*, 9(2), 65-74.
- GAISE College Report ASA Revision Committee (2016) “Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistics Education College Report 2016,” <http://www.amstat.org/education/gaise>.
- Haldar, LC, Wong, N, Heller, JI, & Konold, C (2018). Students making sense of multi-level data. *Technology Innovations in Statistics Education*, 11(1).
- Lazic, S. E. (2010). “The problem of pseudoreplication in neuroscientific studies: is it affecting your analysis?”. *BMC neuroscience*, 11, 1-17.
- Lazic, S, Clarke-Williams, C, and Munafò, M. (2018). “What exactly is ‘N’ in cell culture and animal experiments?”. *PLOS Biology*, 16(4), p.e2005282.
- Leisch, F, Weingessel, A and Hornik, K (2021). “bindata: Generation of Artificial Binary Data”. R package version 0.9-20. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=bindata>.
- Sato, S, Omori, Y, Katoh, K, Kondo, M, Kanagawa, M, Miyata, K, Funabiki, K, Koyasu, T, Kajimura, N, Miyoshi, T, Sawai, H, Kobayashi, K, Tani, A, Toda, T, Usukura, J, Tano, Y, Fujikado, T, & Furukawa, T. (2008). “Pikachurin, a dystroglycan ligand, is essential for Photoreceptor Ribbon Synapse Formation”. *Nature Neuroscience*, 11(8), 923–931. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.2160>.
- Schömig, F, Bürger, J, Hu, Z, Pruß, A, Klotz, E, Pumberger, M, and Hipfl, C (2021). “Intraoperative blood loss as indicated by haemoglobin trend is a predictor for the development of postoperative spinal implant infection—a matched-pair analysis”. *Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery and Research*, 16(393).
- Tong, L, White, BJG, & Singh, J (2022) “Bridging statistics and life sciences undergraduate education”. *Journal of Biological Education*, 1-13.
- Tractenberg, R (2022). *Ethical Reasoning for a Data-Centered World: Ethical Reasoning for a Data-Centered World*. Ethics International Press.
- Weissgerber TL, Garovic VD, Milin-Lazovic JS, Winham SJ, Obradovic Z, Trzeciakowski JP, Milic, NM. (2016) “Reinventing Biostatistics Education for Basic Scientists”. *PLoS Biol*. 14(4): e1002430. doi:10.1371/journal.pbio.1002430.
- White, BJG, & Singh, J (2021, July 1). “Partnering to Prepare Tomorrow’s Life Sciences Researchers” [Poster Presentation]. United States Conference on Teaching Statistics (USCOTS) 2021. <https://www.causeweb.org/cause/uscots/uscots21/th-03-partnering-prepare-tomorrow%E2%80%99s-life-sciences-researchers>.
- Wickham, H (2021). *Mastering shiny*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.